

Remapping the Livonian Coast: A Multilingual Gazetteer of the Settlements of Northern Kurzeme

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We began by constructing a multilingual geographic reconciliation layer—a gazetteer—to align historical and modern place names (e.g., *Mazirbe*, *Irē*, *Mazupõe*) under canonical identifiers. While this resembles standard geocoding, our approach integrates multi-script, multi-ethnic, and historical variants. The gazetteer draws from public sources such as GeoNames, national databases, and historical atlases, and is manually verified in collaboration with Finno-Ugric scholars to ensure cultural nuance.

We selected the Livonian coast as a prototype due to its manageable scale—roughly a dozen villages where Livonian was still spoken in the late 19th century. Using the *Livonian Place Name Catalogue* (Ernštreits 2020) as a starting point for Livonian and Latvian names, we compiled historical and contemporary names across languages: Livonian, Latvian, Estonian, Finnish, Hungarian, Russian, and Baltic German. This cross-linguistic layering increases the chance of surfacing relevant materials in collections that use inconsistent or outdated place names.

Even within this small region, the variation is significant. For example, *Mazirbe* (Livonian: *Irē*) and *Lielirbe* (*Īra*) appear in metadata as *Irben*, *Gross-Irben*, *Klein-Irben*, *Suuri-Irben* (Finnish-German hybrid), or *Irē*. Diacritical and orthographic shifts—like *Īra* (Latvian) vs. *Īra* (Hungarian)—complicate exact matching. Soviet-era sources followed standardized Latvian forms, while imperial Russian materials preserved German exonyms. These linguistic, political, and orthographic layers show why rigid top-down normalization is impractical.

Our work draws on and extends existing approaches. Wikibase has proven effective for multilingual authority control (Bianchini, Bargioni, and Pellizzari di San Girolamo 2021; Fagervig 2023). The *AvoingLAM* initiative, for example, imported Sámi toponyms into Wikidata, showing how Wikibase can support culturally grounded reconciliation. We generalize and expand these models for Finno-Ugric contexts.

We used this Gazetteer for the creation of (Pigozne, Antal, and Mester 2025).

1. Why a Gazetteer for the Livonian Coast?

A *gazetteer* is a structured list or database of place names — often enriched with geographic coordinates, historical context, and multilingual labels. In the digital humanities, gazetteers serve as foundational reference tools for *mapping*, *text annotation*, *archival description*, and *linked data integration*.

For the *Livonian coast*, creating such a gazetteer was especially necessary because:

- This narrow coastal region is home to the *Livonian minority*, a nearly extinct Finno-Ugric people with a *rich but under-documented toponymy*.
- Many historical settlements — even some still recognized today — have *multiple names* in Livonian, Latvian, Russian, German, and Finnish, depending on the period and source.
- Over the 19th and 20th centuries, *administrative boundaries changed frequently*, often obscuring or erasing older names from modern records.
- Place names appear in *textile provenance*, *ethnographic studies*, and *oral histories*, but lack a reliable, linked reference model for digital use.

This gazetteer offers a *structured, multilingual, and semantically linked dataset* that allows scholars, heritage professionals, and digital tools to *refer unambiguously to places* on the Livonian coast — past and present.

Heritage metadata is often treated as fixed: accession-era knowledge published as RDF and rarely revisited, and this leads to search difficulties: Aladár Bán’s Estonian collection items in the Museum of Ethnography in Budapest can be found in “Russia”, in itself, an ambiguous term that means both the historical Russian Empire and the current Russian Federation, even if the provenance lies in modern Estonia. A.O. Heikels collection artefacts from the Livonian Coast in the Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland may be attributed to *Suur-Irben* (and Russia, again), a name variation of *Lielirbe* that is certainly not to be found on any

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map created in the last 100 years. (See for example: *liiviläinen morsian; [Livonian bride (SUK15:85)]* (Heikel 1902))

Our aim with the gazetteer to help researchers connecting digital surrogates, secondary sources, and data across databases that do not use normalised geographical names. We also hope that this is a first step to provide semantic feedback for data curators and collection managers in museums, archives and libraries.

The world's perhaps greatest humanities researcher, <https://whgazetteer.org/> does not contain much information about Mazirbe (Grossner, Grunewald, and Mostern 2022), showing the importance of mapping local knowledge.

2. How to use the Gazetteer?

The screenshot shows the Wikibase interface for the item 'Mazirbe' (Q4202). The page includes a navigation sidebar on the left with options like 'Main page', 'Recent changes', and 'Tools'. The main content area displays the item name, a description 'village in Latvia', and a list of statements. Two statements are visible: 'instance of' with the value 'village in Latvia' and 'part of' with the value 'Livonian coastal villages'. Below these, the 'Identifiers' section shows the Wikidata QID 'Q2667982'. The interface also includes options to edit, add references, and add values.

Try out the Gazetteer on the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Item:Q4202>

Each place entry in our gazetteer is published as a structured document in the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space. These documents are managed using a Wikibase system, the same open-source software that powers Wikidata. Every entry has its own persistent web address and is readable in two main ways:

1. As a human-friendly web page. For example, the settlement of Miķeļtornis (Livonian: Pizā) is available at: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Item:Q4429>
2. As a machine-readable RDF document in standard formats. The same entry can be accessed in:
 - Turtle format: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4429.ttl>
 - RDF/XML format: <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Special:EntityData/Q4429.rdf>

These structured entries contain multilingual labels and aliases. For example, the entry for Lielirbe includes:

```
wd:Q4429          rdfs:label          "Lielirbe"@en      ;
rdfs:label        "Īra"@liv           ;
skos:prefLabel    "Īra"@liv .
```

This tells us that the modern name in English is Lielirbe (also the official Latvian name), while the Livonian name is Īra. In some cases, we also include historical or unusual names as aliases:

```
wd:Q4429 skos:altLabel "Suur-Irben"@fi .
```

This Finnish name was found in a museum record and illustrates how rare historical variants are captured and preserved. These records enable both humans and digital tools to reliably work across languages, scripts, and time periods when referring to places on the Livonian coast (Lībiešu krasts/Līvōd rānda.)

Latvian	Livonian	Russian	German	HTML	TTL
Lībiešu krasts	Līvōd rānda	Ливский берег	Livländische Küste	fuds:Q4389	fuds:Q4389.ttl
Jaunciems	Ūžkilā	Яунциемс		fuds:Q4428	fuds:Q4428.ttl
Kolka	Kūolka	Колка	Kolken	fuds:Q4390	fuds:Q4390.ttl
Košrags	Kuoštrōg			fuds:Q4417	fuds:Q4417.ttl
Lielirbe	Īra	Лиелирбе	Irben Gross- Irben	fuds:Q4429	fuds:Q4429.ttl
Lūžņa	Lūžkilā	Лужня		fuds:Q4424	fuds:Q4424.ttl
Mazirbe	Irē	Мазирбе	Klein-Irben	fuds:Q4427	fuds:Q4427.ttl
Miķeltornis	Pizā	Микельторни с	Pissen	fuds:Q4430	fuds:Q4430.ttl
Saunags	Sānag	Саунагс		fuds:Q4419	fuds:Q4419.ttl
Sīkrags	Sīkrōg	Сикрагс	Zikraggen	fuds:Q4418	fuds:Q4418.ttl
Ūši	Māgkilā			fuds:Q4427	fuds:Q4427.ttl
Vaide	Vaid	Вайде		fuds:Q4393	fuds:Q4393.ttl
Ventspils	Vānta	Вентспилс	Windau	fuds:Q4392	fuds:Q4392.ttl

We also added alternative names, for example, *Lūžņa kylä* (Finnish: Lūžņa village) when this form was used in *Liiviläiset kuuntelevat gramfonille tallennettua kieltään*. [Livonians listen to their language recorded on a gramophone (SUK139:7)] (Kettunen, Lauri 1920)

Lauri Kettunen: Liiviläiset kuuntelevat gramfonille tallennettua kieltään. [Livonians listen to their language recorded on a gramophone (SUK139:7)]

2.1. Interoperability

To support interoperability across heritage platforms, we link each settlement entry in the gazetteer to globally recognized authority services. These identifiers are persistent, resolvable web addresses that connect our local documentation to broader networks of geographic and bibliographic knowledge.

2.1.1. GeoNames

Where available, we include a GeoNames identifier — a widely used geographical reference system. For example, the village of Lielirbe is linked to:

<https://www.geonames.org/458007/lielirbe.html>

In RDF, this appears as:

```
wd:Q4429 owl:sameAs <https://sws.geonames.org/458007/> .
```

This allows researchers and software to recognize that Lielirbe in our dataset corresponds to the same location used in global GIS tools, library catalogs, and historical maps.

The screenshot shows the GeoNames website interface. At the top, there is a search bar with the text 'Paris, Mount Everest, New York' and a search icon. Below the search bar, the page title is 'Lielirbe - to view map click on map icon in bottom toolbar. (we need to reduce the cost for the map views)'. There are several navigation tabs: 'Feature', 'Hierarchy', 'History', 'Tags', and 'Alternate names' (which is highlighted in blue). Below the tabs is a table of alternate names. The table has columns for 'code', 'lang', 'alternate name', 'p.', 's.', 'h.', 'c.', 'from', 'to', and 'action'. The table contains the following rows:

code	lang	alternate name	p.	s.	h.	c.	from	to	action
		Gross Irben							+
link	link to website	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lielirbe							+ ✎ ✕
		Lielirbe							+ ✎ ✕
		Lielirbes Ciems							+ ✎ ✕
		Liyelirbe							+ ✎ ✕

Below the table, there is a note: 'The language code is referring to the ISO-639-2 and ISO-639-3 codes.' and a list of language codes: 'en (english)', 'fr (french)', and '...'. To the right of this note is a legend for the table columns: 'p. = preferred', 's. = short', 'h. = historical', and 'c. = colloquial'.

GeoNames also contains alternative names; it also has information about the current administrative territorial unit, geocoordinates, population, elevation, and other geographical information that can help identifying unambiguously Lielirbe.

2.1.2. VIAF

For culturally or historically significant settlements that appear in catalog records, we also link to VIAF (Virtual International Authority File). VIAF integrates national library data to support name disambiguation and discovery. For example, Mazirbe has the VIAF ID:

<https://viaf.org/viaf/153822754>

Which we reference as:

```
wd:Q4428 owl:sameAs <http://viaf.org/viaf/153822754> .
```

This helps users discover books, ethnographies, and archival material related to that settlement, even across different cataloging systems and languages.

Search

Select Field: All Headings | Select Index: All VIAF | Search Terms: *

SEARCH

Mazirbe (Talsu novads, Latvija)

Mazirbe

Mazirbe (Latvia)

Latvia Mazirbe

VIAF ID: 153822754 (Geographic)

Permalink: <http://viaf.org/viaf/153822754>

Preferred Forms

 151 #a Latvia #z Mazirbe

 151 #a Mazirbe

 151 #a Mazirbe (Latvia)

 151 #a Mazirbe (Talsu novads, Latvija)

In the VIAF system we often find slightly different preferred names for Mazirbe in various national library systems.

2.1.3. Wikidata

We also connect entries to Wikidata, the central hub of linked data maintained by the Wikimedia Foundation. For places that already existed in Wikidata, we added their QID. If no entry existed — as in the case of smaller or abandoned settlements like Ūši — we created a new Wikidata item to ensure inclusion.

Example:

wd:Q4429 owl:sameAs wd:Q13277032 .

These links position the Livonian gazetteer within the broader semantic web, making it easier to query, visualize, and cross-reference in digital humanities and cultural heritage workflows.

Wikidata connects many knowledge sources and information services, and often refers to the encyclopedic description about Mazirbe or provides images of Mazirbe.

3. Administrative Entities

Wherever possible, we have linked each settlement to its current administrative territorial entity using the standard property `wdt:P131`. This helps users situate the place within today’s Latvian municipal structure. For example, the historical, now largely abandoned village of *Lielirbe* is currently within *Ventspils Municipality*, and is represented in RDF as:

```
wd:Q4429 wdt:P131 wd:Q217434 .
```

This allows the gazetteer to support queries and filters by present-day jurisdictions.

However, we caution users that administrative boundaries along the Livonian coast have changed repeatedly over the last two centuries. These changes span:

- The Russian Imperial period
- Latvia’s first independence (1918–1940)
- The Nazi German and Soviet occupations
- Post-Soviet municipal reforms after 1991

Even at the parish level, names and boundaries were redrawn multiple times, often with language-specific variants (e.g., German, Russian, Latvian, Livonian) appearing in parallel. For example, a single parish may appear as *Mazirbes pagasts*, *Irben*, or *Irbenhof* depending on the source and time period.

To address this, we plan to extend the gazetteer with:

- Historical administrative layers
- Start and end dates for each jurisdiction
- Multilingual aliases for parish and municipality names

This future enhancement will allow researchers to trace both the spatial and temporal context of a settlement more precisely, especially when working with historical maps, land records, or ethnographic sources.

4. References

Bianchini, Carlo, Stefano Bargioni, and Camillo Carlo Pellizzari di San Girolamo. 2021. “Beyond VIAF Wikidata as a Complementary Tool for Authority Control in Libraries.” *Information Technology and Libraries* 40 (2). <https://doi.org/10.6017/ital.v40i2.12959>.

Ernštreits, Valts. 2020. “Livonian Place Names: Documentation, Problems, and Opportunities.” *Eesti Ja Soome-Ugri Keeleteaduse Ajakiri. Journal of Estonian and Finno-Ugric Linguistics* 11 (1): 213–33. <https://doi.org/10.12697/jeful.2020.11.1.09>.

Fagervig, Alicia. 2023. “Wikidata for Authority Control: Sharing Museum Knowledge with the World.” *Digital Humanities in the Nordic and Baltic Countries Publications* 5 (1): 222–39. <https://doi.org/10.5617/dhnbpub.10665>.

Grossner, Karl, Susan Grunewald, and Ruth Mostern. 2022. “Bringing Places from the Distant Past to the Present: A Report on the World Historical Gazetteer.” *Int. J. Digit. Libr.* 24 (3): 159–62. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-022-00341-2>.

Heikel, Axel Olai. 1902. *liiviläinen morsian; [Livonian bride (SUK15:85)]: Part of the Finno-Ugric Collections (National Museum of Finland) and the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space (Q4664)*. <https://www.finna.fi/Record/museovirasto.21e4b5ec-b9b8-4064-96e7-dba43e075b64>.

Kettunen, Lauri. 1920. *Liiviläiset kuuntelevat gramfonille tallennettua kieltään. [Livonians listen to their language recorded on a gramophone (SUK139:7)]: Part of the Finno-Ugric Collection of the National Museum of Finland and the Finno-Ugric Data Sharing Space*. <https://reprexbase.eu/fu/Item:Q4667>.

Pigozne, Ieva, Daniel Antal, and Anna Márta Mester. 2025. “Linked Open Datasets on Traditional Livonian Clothing.” *TextileBase*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15668562>.